

**Barcelona
Supercomputing
Center**
Centro Nacional de Supercomputación

DrugProt Large Scale corpus collection criteria and protocol

Antonio Miranda-Escalada (0000-0002-5654-001X),

Martin Krallinger (0000-0002-2646-8782)

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

DrugProt Large Scale corpus collection

Hits for the following search queries were retrieved, the selection was limited to results from the last 10 years and only included a subselection to these records with abstracts (and potentially labelled with human as species MeSH subset).

For the selection of a relevant subset of PubMed records several criteria were initially considered, including:

Criteria 1: Topic-based selection (MeSH term queries)

- A. receptors, drug[MeSH Terms]
- B. antiviral agents[MeSH Terms]
- C. ("Blood Proteins/abnormalities"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/analogs and derivatives"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/pharmacology"[Mesh] OR "Blood Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- D. ("Carrier Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/analogs and derivatives"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/pathology"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/pharmacology"[Mesh] OR "Carrier Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- E. ("Cell Cycle Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Cell Cycle Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Cell Cycle Proteins/analogs and derivatives"[Mesh] OR "Cell Cycle Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Cell Cycle Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Cell Cycle Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Cell Cycle Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Cell Cycle Proteins/pharmacology"[Mesh] OR "Cell Cycle Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- F. ("Cerebrospinal Fluid Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Cerebrospinal Fluid Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Cerebrospinal Fluid Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Cerebrospinal Fluid Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Cerebrospinal Fluid Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Cerebrospinal Fluid Proteins/pharmacology"[Mesh] OR "Cerebrospinal Fluid Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- G. ("Colipases/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Colipases/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Colipases/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Colipases/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Colipases/pharmacology"[Mesh] OR "Colipases/toxicity"[Mesh])

- H. ("Contractile Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Contractile Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Contractile Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Contractile Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Contractile Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Contractile Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Contractile Proteins/pharmacology"[Mesh] OR "Contractile Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- I. ("Cystatins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Cystatins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Cystatins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Cystatins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Cystatins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Cystatins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- J. ("Cytoskeletal Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Cytoskeletal Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Cytoskeletal Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Cytoskeletal Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Cytoskeletal Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Cytoskeletal Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- K. ("DNA-Binding Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "DNA-Binding Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "DNA-Binding Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "DNA-Binding Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "DNA-Binding Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "DNA-Binding Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- L. ("Eye Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Eye Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Eye Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Eye Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Eye Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Eye Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Eye Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- M. ("Fanconi Anemia Complementation Group Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Fanconi Anemia Complementation Group Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Fanconi Anemia Complementation Group Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Fanconi Anemia Complementation Group Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Fanconi Anemia Complementation Group Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Fanconi Anemia Complementation Group Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh])
- N. ("Flavoproteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Flavoproteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Flavoproteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Flavoproteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Flavoproteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Flavoproteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- O. ("Globulins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Globulins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Globulins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Globulins/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Globulins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Globulins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Globulins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- P. ("Glycoproteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Glycoproteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Glycoproteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Glycoproteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Glycoproteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Glycoproteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Glycoproteins/toxicity"[Mesh])

- Q. ("Cytochromes/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Cytochromes/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Cytochromes/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Cytochromes/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Cytochromes/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Cytochromes/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Cytochromes/pharmacology"[Mesh] OR "Cytochromes/toxicity"[Mesh])
- R. ("Huntingtin Protein/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Huntingtin Protein/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Huntingtin Protein/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Huntingtin Protein/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Huntingtin Protein/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Huntingtin Protein/toxicity"[Mesh])
- S. ("Immediate-Early Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Immediate-Early Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Immediate-Early Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Immediate-Early Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Immediate-Early Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Immediate-Early Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Immediate-Early Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- T. ("Immune Checkpoint Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Immune Checkpoint Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Immune Checkpoint Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Immune Checkpoint Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Immune Checkpoint Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Immune Checkpoint Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Immune Checkpoint Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- U. ("Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- V. ("Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Intercellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- W. ("Intracellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Intracellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Intracellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Intracellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Intracellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Intracellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Intracellular Signaling Peptides and Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])

- X. ("Intrinsically Disordered Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Intrinsically Disordered Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Intrinsically Disordered Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Intrinsically Disordered Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh])
- Y. ("Iodoproteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Iodoproteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Iodoproteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Iodoproteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Iodoproteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Iodoproteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- Z. ("Iron-Regulatory Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Iron-Regulatory Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Iron-Regulatory Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Iron-Regulatory Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Iron-Regulatory Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Iron-Regulatory Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh])
- AA.("LDL-Receptor Related Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "LDL-Receptor Related Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "LDL-Receptor Related Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "LDL-Receptor Related Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "LDL-Receptor Related Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "LDL-Receptor Related Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "LDL-Receptor Related Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- BB.("LIM Domain Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "LIM Domain Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "LIM Domain Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "LIM Domain Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "LIM Domain Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh])
- CC. ("Lipoproteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Lipoproteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Lipoproteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Lipoproteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Lipoproteins/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Lipoproteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Lipoproteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Lipoproteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- DD. ("Membrane Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Membrane Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Membrane Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Membrane Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Membrane Proteins/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Membrane Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Membrane Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Membrane Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- EE.("Metalloproteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Metalloproteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Metalloproteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Metalloproteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Metalloproteins/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Metalloproteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Metalloproteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Metalloproteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- FF. ("Mitochondrial Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Mitochondrial Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Mitochondrial Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Mitochondrial Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Mitochondrial Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Mitochondrial Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Mitochondrial Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])

- GG. ("Molecular Chaperones/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Molecular Chaperones/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Molecular Chaperones/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Molecular Chaperones/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Molecular Chaperones/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Molecular Chaperones/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Molecular Chaperones/toxicity"[Mesh])
- HH. ("Mutant Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Mutant Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Mutant Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Mutant Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Mutant Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Mutant Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Mutant Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- II. ("Neoplasm Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasm Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasm Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasm Proteins/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasm Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh])
- JJ. ("Nerve Tissue Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Nerve Tissue Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Nerve Tissue Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Nerve Tissue Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Nerve Tissue Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Nerve Tissue Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Nerve Tissue Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- KK. ("Nuclear Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Nuclear Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Nuclear Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Nuclear Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Nuclear Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Nuclear Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Nuclear Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- LL. ("Nucleoproteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Nucleoproteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Nucleoproteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Nucleoproteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Nucleoproteins/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Nucleoproteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Nucleoproteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Nucleoproteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- MM. ("Oxidative Phosphorylation Coupling Factors/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Oxidative Phosphorylation Coupling Factors/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Oxidative Phosphorylation Coupling Factors/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Oxidative Phosphorylation Coupling Factors/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Oxidative Phosphorylation Coupling Factors/metabolism"[Mesh])
- NN. ("Parkinson Disease Associated Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Parkinson Disease Associated Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Parkinson Disease Associated Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Parkinson Disease Associated Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Parkinson Disease Associated Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Parkinson Disease Associated Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Parkinson Disease Associated Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])

- OO. ("Phosphoproteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR
"Phosphoproteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Phosphoproteins/antagonists and
inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Phosphoproteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR
"Phosphoproteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Phosphoproteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR
"Phosphoproteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- PP. ("Pregnancy Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Pregnancy
Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Pregnancy Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh]
OR "Pregnancy Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Pregnancy
Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Pregnancy Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR
"Pregnancy Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- QQ. ("Prions/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Prions/agonists"[Mesh] OR
"Prions/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Prions/drug effects"[Mesh] OR
"Prions/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Prions/genetics"[Mesh] OR
"Prions/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Prions/toxicity"[Mesh])
- RR. ("Pulmonary Surfactant-Associated Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR
"Pulmonary Surfactant-Associated Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Pulmonary
Surfactant-Associated Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Pulmonary
Surfactant-Associated Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Pulmonary
Surfactant-Associated Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Pulmonary
Surfactant-Associated Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Pulmonary
Surfactant-Associated Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- SS. ("Receptors, Cytoplasmic and Nuclear/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Receptors,
Cytoplasmic and Nuclear/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Receptors, Cytoplasmic and
Nuclear/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Receptors, Cytoplasmic and
Nuclear/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Receptors, Cytoplasmic and
Nuclear/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Receptors, Cytoplasmic and
Nuclear/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Receptors, Cytoplasmic and Nuclear/toxicity"[Mesh]
)
- TT. ("Recombinant Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Recombinant
Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Recombinant Proteins/antagonists and
inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Recombinant Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Recombinant
Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Recombinant Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR
"Recombinant Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- UU. ("Ribosomal Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Ribosomal
Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Ribosomal Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh]
OR "Ribosomal Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Ribosomal
Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Ribosomal Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR
"Ribosomal Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])
- VV. ("Salivary Proteins and Peptides/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Salivary Proteins and
Peptides/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Salivary Proteins and Peptides/antagonists and
inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Salivary Proteins and Peptides/drug effects"[Mesh] OR

"Salivary Proteins and Peptides/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Salivary Proteins and Peptides/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Salivary Proteins and Peptides/toxicity"[Mesh])

WW. ("Scleroproteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Scleroproteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Scleroproteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Scleroproteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Scleroproteins/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Scleroproteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Scleroproteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Scleroproteins/toxicity"[Mesh])

XX.("Secretoglobins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Secretoglobins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Secretoglobins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Secretoglobins/metabolism"[Mesh])

YY.("Selenium-Binding Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Selenium-Binding Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Selenium-Binding Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh])

ZZ. ("Selenoproteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Selenoproteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Selenoproteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Selenoproteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Selenoproteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Selenoproteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Selenoproteins/toxicity"[Mesh])

AAA. ("Seminal Plasma Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Seminal Plasma Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Seminal Plasma Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Seminal Plasma Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Seminal Plasma Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Seminal Plasma Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Seminal Plasma Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])

BBB. ("Serpins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Serpins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Serpins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Serpins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Serpins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Serpins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Serpins/toxicity"[Mesh])

CCC. "Silver Proteins"[Mesh]

DDD. ("Thioredoxins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Thioredoxins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Thioredoxins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Thioredoxins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Thioredoxins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Thioredoxins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Thioredoxins/toxicity"[Mesh])

EEE. ("Thymosin/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Thymosin/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Thymosin/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Thymosin/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Thymosin/toxicity"[Mesh])

FFF. ("Transcription Factors/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Transcription Factors/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Transcription Factors/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Transcription Factors/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Transcription Factors/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Transcription Factors/metabolism"[Mesh] OR

"Transcription Factors/therapeutic use"[Mesh] OR "Transcription Factors/toxicity"[Mesh])

GGG. ("Tripartite Motif Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Tripartite Motif Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Tripartite Motif Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Tripartite Motif Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Tripartite Motif Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Tripartite Motif Proteins/therapeutic use"[Mesh])

HHH. ("Ubiquitinated Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitinated Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitinated Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitinated Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitinated Proteins/therapeutic use"[Mesh])

III. ("Ubiquitins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Ubiquitins/toxicity"[Mesh])

JJJ. ("Viral Proteins/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Viral Proteins/agonists"[Mesh] OR "Viral Proteins/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Viral Proteins/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Viral Proteins/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Viral Proteins/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Viral Proteins/toxicity"[Mesh])

KKK. "antagonists and inhibitors" [Subheading]

LLL. "agonists" [Subheading]

MMM. "Cytochrome-B(5) Reductase"[Mesh]

Criteria 2: Gene/proteinNER entity-based selection criteria (association of records to genes derived from NER systems, i.e GnormPlus)

Criteria 3: Drug/chemical entity based selection (association of records to drugs/chemicals)

A. "Drug Interactions"[Mesh]

B. "Drug-Related Side Effects and Adverse Reactions"[Mesh]

C. "Drug Partial Agonism"[Mesh]

D. "Drug Inverse Agonism"[Mesh]

E. "Drug Synergism"[Mesh]

- F. "Drug Antagonism"[Mesh]
- G. "Chemical and Drug Induced Liver Injury"[Mesh]
- H. "Drug Agonism"[Mesh]
- I. "Herb-Drug Interactions"[Mesh]
- J. "Drug Resistance, Multiple, Viral"[Mesh]
- K. "Drug Resistance, Viral"[Mesh]
- L. "Food-Drug Interactions"[Mesh]
- M. "Inactivation, Metabolic"[Mesh]
- N. "Illicit Drugs"[Mesh]
- O. "Metabolic Side Effects of Drugs and Substances"[Mesh]
- P. "Prodrugs"[Mesh]
- Q. "Antimalarials"[Mesh]
- R. "Angiogenesis Inhibitors"[Mesh]
- S. "Multidrug Resistance-Associated Proteins"[Mesh]
- T. "COVID-19 drug treatment" [Supplementary Concept]
- U. "Cytostatic Agents"[Mesh]
- V. "Activation, Metabolic"[Mesh]
- W. "Antimitotic Agents"[Mesh]
- X. "Metabolic Detoxication, Phase I"[Mesh]
- Y. "Antiviral Agents"[Mesh]
- Z. "Pharmacogenomic Variants"[Mesh]
- AA."Antiretroviral Therapy, Highly Active"[Mesh]

Criteria 4: Knowledge-base selection criteria (records derived from citations in biological databases related to genes)

PMIDs from GeneRif and UniProt (with particular species constraints)

Criteria 5: Classifier-based selection criteria (gene-regulation records)

PMIDs from TGR abstract classifier (EXTRI)

Criteria 6: Species-based selection criteria (association of records to certain species/taxonomic criteria)

- A. ("Viruses/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Viruses/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Viruses/metabolism"[Mesh])

- B. ("Coronaviridae/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Coronaviridae/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Coronaviridae/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Coronaviridae/metabolism"[Mesh])

Criteria 7: Disease-based selection criteria

"COVID-19"[Mesh]

"Rare Diseases"[Mesh]

"Diseases Category"[Mesh]

Criteria 8: Chemical NER entity-based selection criteria (, i.e tmChem)

Records linked to chemical entities through tmChem results (FTP)

Criteria 9: Pharmacological action-based selection criteria

- A. "14-alpha Demethylase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]
- B. "5-alpha Reductase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]
- C. "5-Lipoxygenase-Activating Protein Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]
- D. "Acetaldehyde Dehydrogenase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]
- E. "Acetylcholine Release Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]
- F. "Acid Sensing Ion Channel Blockers" [Pharmacological Action]

- G. "Adenosine A1 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- H. "Adenosine A1 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- I. "Adenosine A2 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- J. "Adenosine A2 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- K. "Adenosine A3 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- L. "Adenosine A3 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- M. "Adenosine Deaminase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]
- N. "Adenylyl Cyclase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]
- O. "Adrenergic Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- P. "Adrenergic alpha-1 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- Q. "Adrenergic alpha-1 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- R. "Adrenergic alpha-2 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- S. "Adrenergic alpha-2 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- T. "Adrenergic alpha-Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- U. "Adrenergic alpha-Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- V. "Adrenergic Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- W. "Adrenergic beta-1 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- X. "Adrenergic beta-1 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- Y. "Adrenergic beta-2 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- Z. "Adrenergic beta-2 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- AA."Adrenergic beta-3 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- BB."Adrenergic beta-3 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- CC. "Adrenergic beta-Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]
- DD. "Adrenergic beta-Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

EE. "Adrenergic Uptake Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

FF. "Androgen Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

GG. "Androgen Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

HH. "Angiogenesis Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

II. "Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

JJ. "Angiotensin II Type 1 Receptor Blockers" [Pharmacological Action]

KK. "Angiotensin II Type 2 Receptor Blockers" [Pharmacological Action]

LL. "Angiotensin Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

MM. "Anti-HIV Agents" [Pharmacological Action]

NN. "Anti-Retroviral Agents" [Pharmacological Action]

OO. "Antidiuretic Hormone Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

PP. "Antimetabolites" [Pharmacological Action]

QQ. "Aromatase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

RR. "beta-Lactamase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

SS. "Bradykinin B1 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

TT. "Bradykinin B2 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

UU. "Bradykinin Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

VV. "Calcineurin Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

WW. "Calcitonin Gene-Related Peptide Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

XX. "Calcium Channel Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

YY. "Calcium Channel Blockers" [Pharmacological Action]

ZZ. "Cannabinoid Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

AAA. "Cannabinoid Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

BBB. "Cannabinoid Receptor Modulators" [Pharmacological Action]

CCC. "Carbonic Anhydrase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

DDD. "Caspase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

EEE. "Catechol O-Methyltransferase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

FFF. "CCR5 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

GGG. "Cholinergic Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

HHH. "Cholinergic Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

III. "Cholinesterase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

JJJ. "Cholinesterase Reactivators" [Pharmacological Action]

KKK. "Cyclooxygenase 2 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

LLL. "Cyclooxygenase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

MMM. "Cysteine Proteinase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

NNN. "Chloride Channel Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

OOO. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP1A2 Inducers" [Pharmacological Action]

PPP. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP1A2 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

QQQ. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2B6 Inducers" [Pharmacological Action]

RRR. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2B6 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

SSS. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2C19 Inducers" [Pharmacological Action]

TTT. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2C19 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

UUU. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2C8 Inducers" [Pharmacological Action]

VVV. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2C8 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

WWW. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2C9 Inducers" [Pharmacological Action]

XXX. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2C9 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

YYY. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2D6 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

ZZZ. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP2E1 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

AAAA. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP3A Inducers" [Pharmacological Action]

BBBB. "Cytochrome P-450 CYP3A Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

CCCC. "Cytochrome P-450 Enzyme Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

DDDD. "Dipeptidyl-Peptidase IV Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

EEEE. "Dopamine Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

FFFF. "Dopamine Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

GGGG. "Dopamine D2 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

HHHH. "Dopamine Uptake Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

IIII. "Endothelin A Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

JJJJ. "Endothelin B Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

KKKK. "Endothelin Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

LLLL. "Enzyme Activators" [Pharmacological Action]

MMMM. "Epithelial Sodium Channel Blockers" [Pharmacological Action]

NNNN. "Estrogen Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

OOOO. "Estrogen Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

PPPP. "Estrogen Receptor Modulators" [Pharmacological Action]

QQQQ. "Excitatory Amino Acid Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

RRRR. "Excitatory Amino Acid Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

SSSS. "Factor Xa Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

TTTT. "Folic Acid Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

UUUU. "GABA-A Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

VVVV. "GABA-A Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

WWWW. "GABA Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

XXXX. "GABA Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

YYYY. "GABA-B Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

ZZZZ. "GABA-B Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

AAAAA. "Glycoside Hydrolase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

BBBBB. "Guanylyl Cyclase C Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

CCCCC. "Heparin Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

DDDDD. "Histamine Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

EEEE. "Histamine Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

FFFFF. "Histamine H1 Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

GGGGG. "Histamine H1 Antagonists, Non-Sedating" [Pharmacological Action]

HHHHH. "Histamine H2 Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

IIIII. "Histamine H3 Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

JJJJJ. "Histone Deacetylase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

KKKKK. "HIV Integrase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

LLLLL. "HIV Protease Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

MMMMM. "Hormone Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

NNNNN. "Hydroxymethylglutaryl-CoA Reductase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

OOOOO. "Insulin Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

PPPPP. "Integrase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

QQQQQ. "Interferon Inducers" [Pharmacological Action]

RRRRR. "Janus Kinase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

SSSSS. "Leukotriene Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

TTTTT. "Lipoprotein Lipase Activators" [Pharmacological Action]

UUUUU. "Lipoxygenase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

VVVVV. "Matrix Metalloproteinase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

WWWWW. "Mineralocorticoid Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

XXXXX. "Monoamine Oxidase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

YYYYY. "Muscarinic Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

ZZZZZ. "Muscarinic Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

AAAAA. "Myeloablative Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

BBBBB. "Narcotic Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

CCCCC. "Neurokinin-1 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

DDDDD. "Nicotinic Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

EEEEE. "Nicotinic Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

FFFFF. "Orexin Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

GGGGG. "Ornithine Decarboxylase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

HHHHH. "Phosphodiesterase 3 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

IIIII. "Phosphodiesterase 4 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

JJJJJ. "Phosphodiesterase 5 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

KKKKK. "Phosphodiesterase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

LLLLL. "Phosphoinositide-3 Kinase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

MMMMM. "Phospholipase A2 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

NNNNN. "Poly(ADP-ribose) Polymerase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

OOOOO. "Potassium Channel Blockers" [Pharmacological Action]

PPPPP. "Prolyl-Hydroxylase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

QQQQQ. "Prostaglandin Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

RRRRR. "Protease Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

SSSSS. "Protein Kinase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

TTTTTT. "Proton Pump Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

UUUUUU. "Purinergeric Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

VVVVVV. "Purinergeric Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

WWWWWW. "Purinergeric P1 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

XXXXXX. "Purinergeric P1 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

YYYYYY. "Purinergeric P2 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

ZZZZZZ. "Purinergeric P2 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

AAAAAAA. "Purinergeric P2X Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

BBBBBBB. "Purinergeric P2Y Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

CCCCCCC. "Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

DDDDDDD. "Serine Proteinase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

EEEEEEE. "Serotonin 5-HT1 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

FFFFFFF. "Serotonin 5-HT1 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

GGGGGGG. "Serotonin 5-HT2 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

HHHHHHH. "Serotonin 5-HT2 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

IIIIIII. "Serotonin 5-HT3 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

JJJJJJJ. "Serotonin 5-HT3 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

KKKKKKK. "Serotonin 5-HT4 Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

LLLLLLL. "Serotonin 5-HT4 Receptor Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

MMMMMMM. "Serotonin Antagonists" [Pharmacological Action]

NNNNNNN. "Serotonin Receptor Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

OOOOOOO. "Sodium Channel Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

PPPPPPP. "Sodium Channel Blockers" [Pharmacological Action]

QQQQQQQ. "Sodium Chloride Symporter Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

RRRRRRR. "Sodium-Glucose Transporter 2 Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

SSSSSSS. "Sodium Potassium Chloride Symporter Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

TTTTTTT. "Sphingosine 1 Phosphate Receptor Modulators" [Pharmacological Action]

UUUUUUU. "Topoisomerase I Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

VVVVVVV. "Topoisomerase II Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

WWWWWWW. "Trypsin Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

XXXXXXX. "Vasopeptidase Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

YYYYYYY. "Viral Protease Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action]

ZZZZZZZ. "Voltage-Gated Sodium Channel Agonists" [Pharmacological Action]

AAAAAAA. "Voltage-Gated Sodium Channel Blockers" [Pharmacological Action]

Criteria 10: Additional gene list and MeSH terms

a)
genelist.txt

b)

- A. "Inflammation"[Mesh]
- B. "Cytokine Release Syndrome"[Mesh]
- C. ("Neoplasms/antagonists and inhibitors"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasms/genetics"[Mesh])
- D. ("Virus Diseases/drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Virus Diseases/drug therapy"[Mesh] OR "Virus Diseases/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Virus Diseases/metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Virus Diseases/therapeutic use"[Mesh])
- E. "Viral Zoonoses"[Mesh]
- F. ("Respiration Disorders/drug therapy"[Mesh] OR "Respiration Disorders/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Respiration Disorders/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Respiration Disorders/metabolism"[Mesh])

G. ("Pneumonia/chemically induced"[Mesh] OR "Pneumonia/congenital"[Mesh] OR "Pneumonia/drug therapy"[Mesh] OR "Pneumonia/enzymology"[Mesh] OR "Pneumonia/genetics"[Mesh] OR "Pneumonia/metabolism"[Mesh])

H. "Macrophage Activation"[Mesh]

Row STATISTICS of PMIDs

Criteria 1:

Rule identifier	unique PMIDs 2011-2021	unique PMIDs all time
A	2796	13911
B	62457	123898
C	267182	746625
D	395543	882564
E	40304	83250
F	155	630
G	22	305
H	43339	112668
I	3074	5080
J	95597	209616
K	241084	470436
L	7913	19562
M	5974	8977
N	17736	37055
O	121475	351483
P	205698	511152
Q	31762	94550
R	826	826
S	3634	10377
T	12755	15621
U	334195	691570
V	334195	691570
W	300468	527780
X	1007	1009
Y	958	3710
Z	1751	2086
AA	1773	2683

BB	3047	3498
CC	36736	109855
DD	587890	1397294
EE	23866	77306
FF	16323	24096
GG	25269	56425
HH	12664	22212
II	145770	282341
JJ	118648	317025
KK	172378	331076
LL	83348	148326
MM	31	142
NN	7578	9531
OO	50907	116702
PP	4520	16617
QQ	3556	8731
RR	1080	2129
SS	59494	128040
TT	52489	191844
UU	9295	23905
VV	1297	2930
WW	46951	117392
XX	395	971
YY	66	91
ZZ	1178	1561
AAA	8491	19434
BBB	8580	29275
CCC	20	134
DDD	1985	4504
EEE	370	1066
FFF	273345	505026
GGG	1063	1063
HHH	359	415
III	8451	19279
JJJ	58109	172619
KKK	208951	525509
LLL	29610	59485

MMM	128	617
TOTAL		

Criteria 3

Rule identifier	unique PMIDs 2011-2021	unique PMIDs all time
A	34132	126723
B	33225	70434
C	251	339
D	328	481
E	16971	54358
F	400	2448
G	8975	19649
H	284	385
I	886	1422
J	292	900
K	6590	12423
L	1086	2182
M	2835	6053
N	4907	10422
O	3002	7913
P	4695	11178
Q	9604	20444
R	13956	22801
S	5968	14200
T	2220	2220
U	429	598
V	371	371
W	2319	3766
X	307	440
Y	62457	123898
Z	983	983
AA	8020	17913
TOTAL		

Criteria 6:

Rule identifier	unique PMIDs 2011-2021	unique PMIDs all time
-----------------	------------------------	-----------------------

A	113791	311531
B	8409	11357
Total		

Criteria 9:

Rule identifier	unique PMIDs 2011-2021	unique PMIDs all time
A	7503	19843
B	1243	3008
C	42	81
D	459	1830
E	5785	13363
F	812	6940
G	171	461
H	289	1623
I	600	1586
J	676	1710
K	111	247
L	90	260
M	151	1330
N	257	2625
O	23203	145655
P	2178	14357
Q	2774	14001
R	5547	20910
S	1524	8267
T	16505	109341
U	5313	37992
V	10305	70381
W	1142	6695
X	2368	12342
Y	3953	15408
Z	199	639
AA	631	995
BB	115	238
CC	11705	75795
DD	10425	59618
EE	10384	43108

FF	4637	13121
GG	771	1356
HH	29617	54745
II	8489	36017
JJ	5809	17081
KK	353	1407
LL	7986	19638
MM	24611	55436
NN	18532	39233
OO	845	1880
PP	95579	272894
QQ	3438	8065
RR	3329	8370
SS	89	216
TT	295	1212
UU	295	1561
VV	10567	34736
WW	321	609
XX	2886	16265
YY	18985	84375
ZZ	4287	9838
AAA	914	2460
BBB	4483	11857
CCC	2617	7471
DDD	5611	14656
EEE	320	1211
FFF	680	1327
GGG	15287	77403
HHH	8228	51017
III	12418	37708
JJJ	484	1911
KKK	4838	12931
LLL	27607	98614
MMM	9389	28767
NNN	510	640
OOO	1637	9164
PPP	8778	33072

QQQ	6429	24744
RRR	37	189
SSS	4465	12557
TTT	7703	17867
UUU	4463	12555
VVV	862	5052
WWW	4468	12560
XXX	5419	15859
YYY	5956	21639
ZZZ	103	337
AAAA	9994	35506
BBBB	10679	28977
CCCC	32119	97368
DDDD	4190	4987
EEEE	5670	28030
FFFF	9142	47625
GGGG	3066	9616
HHHH	13490	46149
IIII	519	1290
JJJJ	337	1080
KKKK	1277	5329
LLLL	5841	12294
MMMM	808	7353
NNNN	9862	32284
OOOO	979	2392
PPPP	6714	23328
QQQQ	4361	23662
RRRR	13229	53339
SSSS	5394	8199
TTTT	12201	41284
UUUU	1879	7298
VVVV	1177	7639
WWWW	3024	12477
XXXX	4981	22384
YYYY	1250	5231
ZZZZ	150	797
AAAAA	2516	4562

BBBBB	220	463
CCCCC	1310	5529
DDDDD	3056	22189
EEEEE	6777	35940
FFFFF	3722	21224
GGGGG	1093	4412
HHHHH	1396	14047
IIIII	267	753
JJJJJ	7652	12238
KKKKK	1875	2726
LLLLL	3779	11112
MMMMM	28841	97286
NNNNN	17113	34056
OOOOO	742	4624
PPPPP	1519	1869
QQQQQ	4487	11268
RRRRR	506	506
SSSSS	1211	4494
TTTTT	8	59
UUUUU	1364	7852
VVVVV	5930	15879
WWWWW	2620	6358
XXXXX	2794	12860
YYYYY	2604	14885
ZZZZZ	5949	35467
AAAAA	11783	44860
BBBBBB	7327	31046
CCCCCC	881	2480
DDDDDD	8319	23802
EEEEEE	2219	16436
FFFFFFF	442	443
GGGGGG	265	2751
HHHHHH	1507	4457
IIIIII	1243	2557
JJJJJJ	3710	6990
KKKKKK	14213	65987
LLLLLL	4270	8921

MMMMMM	374	575
NNNNNN	2879	4668
OOOOOO	4283	18718
PPPPP	174	174
QQQQQQ	1423	4222
RRRRRR	43967	147584
SSSSSS	58981	104544
TTTTTT	6614	15776
UUUUUU	6637	25476
VVVVVV	11932	42501
WWWWWW	6655	25482
XXXXXX	6608	33654
YYYYYY	59	911
ZZZZZZ	5562	10667
AAAAAAA	589	608
BBBBBBB	6041	9994
CCCCCCC	9203	28505
DDDDDDD	17276	59729
EEEEEEE	2477	5261
FFFFFFF	292	699
GGGGGGG	469	797
HHHHHHH	2917	5207
IIIIII	79	140
JJJJJJ	1432	3097
KKKKKKK	232	380
LLLLLLL	42	91
MMMMMMM	9769	41312
NNNNNNN	12146	65176
OOOOOOO	532	1992
PPPPPPP	14005	68034
QQQQQQQ	1588	7680
RRRRRRR	3102	3174
SSSSSSS	1835	10062
TTTTTTT	1649	2226
UUUUUUU	6180	14799
VVVVVVV	35258	100639
WWWWWWW	2947	17989

XXXXXXXX	22	214
YYYYYYY	2984	7112
ZZZZZZZ	463	1359
AAAAAAA	7442	34810
Total		

Criteria 10b

Rule identifier	unique PMIDs 2011-2021	unique PMIDs all time
A	142101	273694
B	857	857
C	232160	420480
D	94214	188633
E	75	75
F	7860	20349
G	17521	28621
H	4889	13538
Total		

Criteria intersection

intersection	intersection explanation	unique PMIDs 2011-2021	unique PMIDs all time
1∩4∩8	proteins queries ∩ uniprot/generif ∩ tmChem	341,682	575,944
1∩4∩3	proteins queries ∩ uniprot/generif ∩ Drug/chemical queries	7,454	12,398
1∩2∩8	proteins queries ∩ gNorm ∩ tmChem	1,234,795	2,807,165
1∩2∩3	proteins queries ∩ gNorm ∩ Drug/chemical queries	72,704	139,816
5∩4∩8	abstract classifier ∩ uniprot/generif ∩ tmChem	122,062	122,062
5∩4∩3	abstract classifier ∩ uniprot/generif ∩ Drug/chemical queries	1,026	1,726
5∩2∩8	abstract classifier ∩ gNorm ∩ tmChem	446,267	446,267
5∩2∩3	abstract classifier ∩ gNorm ∩ Drug/chemical queries	5,600	11,428
6∩4∩8	species queries ∩ uniprot/generif ∩ tmChem	9,048	20,304
6∩4∩3	species queries ∩ uniprot/generif ∩ Drug/chemical queries	706	1,213
6∩2∩8	species queries ∩ gNorm ∩ tmChem	57,507	126,557
6∩2∩3	species queries ∩ gNorm ∩ Drug/chemical queries	9,263	15,820
9∩4∩8	pharmacological action queries ∩ uniprot/generif ∩ tmChem	47,625	85,459
9∩4∩3	pharmacological action queries ∩ uniprot/generif ∩ Drug/chemical queries	3,696	5,898
9∩2∩8	pharmacological action queries ∩ gNorm ∩ tmChem	363,535	915,206
9∩2∩3	pharmacological action queries ∩ gNorm ∩ Drug/chemical queries	52,891	104,731
10B∩4∩8	? ∩ uniprot/generif ∩ tmChem	97,656	135,047
10B∩2∩8	? ∩ gNorm ∩ tmChem	300,000	485,849

10A∩2∩8	NTNU_genelist ∩ gNorm ∩ tmChem	1,551,578	1,551,578
UNION	Union of all the previous intersections (except 10)	1,688,251	3,313,585
UNION+10	Union of all the previous intersections	2,652,503	4,012,544

**We queried PubMed for the 4,012,544 abstracts. Despite the queries required the PubMed IDs to have available abstracts, 45,524 of them (1.1%) did not have available abstract. The final number of downloaded abstracts was 3,971,119.

Brief workflow

1. Define Background set selection Criteria
2. Get PubMed IDs that match the defined queries. In this step, no time filtering was applied.
 - a. Date of Criteria 1 PubMed ID collection: jun 17 12:25 - jun 17 13:04
 - b. Date of Criteria 3 PubMed ID collection: jun 17 12:09 - jun 17 13:02
 - c. Date of Criteria 6 PubMed ID collection: jun 17 14:39 - jun 17 14:39
 - d. Date of Criteria 9 PubMed ID collection: 17 17:37 - jun 17 17:43
 - e. Date of Criteria 10b PubMed ID collection: jun 23 18:58 - jun 23 18:59
3. Generate one set of PubMed IDs per Criteria (the union of the queries)
4. Define intersections criteria
5. Generate one set of PubMed IDs per intersection
6. Generate one final set of PubMed IDs (the union of all intersections)
7. Download the abstracts corresponding to the final set of PubMed IDs
 - a. Date of abstract download: all abstracts from the Criteria 1, 3, 6, 9 and 10B were downloaded in this time window: june23 20:12 - june24 06:31 (madrid time)
8. Remove abstracts already present in DrugProt corpus. Remove as well abstracts that contained the sections "keywords" and "linked articles" (422 records). We will decide later whether to include such sections or not.

Code snippet for final filtering:

```
fout = codecs.open(final_path, 'w', "utf-8")
with codecs.open(original_path, 'r', "utf-8") as f:
    for line in f:
        if int(line.split('\t')[0]) in drugprot_keyw_linked:
            continue
        fout.write(line)
fout.close
```

Script for PubMed abstract dump:

<https://github.com/tonifuc3m/pubmed-parser>